

Dataset | Connected reservoirs: modelling aquatic ecosystems along a cascade system in Brazil

1. Folder Structure

The data for each reservoir (BB, BA, IB, PR, NA, TI) is provided in a separate folder (zipped before upload), containing:

- `*_glm2.nml`` – main GLM configuration file
- `*_aed2.nml`` – AED2 water quality configuration
- `*_aed2_phyto_pars.nml`` – phytoplankton parameter settings
- `*_met_hourly.csv`` – meteorological forcing (hourly resolution)
- `*_inflow.csv`` – inflow boundary conditions
- `*_outflow.csv`` – outflow boundary conditions
- `README.md`` – documentation of variables, units, and usage

2. Data format and units

- Meteorology (`*_met_hourly.csv``): time (YYYY-MM-DD HH:MM), Shortwave (W/m^2), Cloud (0-1), AirTemp ($^{\circ}C$), RelHum (%), WindSpeed (m/s), and Rain (mm/h).
- Inflows (`*_inflow.csv``): time (YYYY-MM-DD), flow (m^3/s), temp ($^{\circ}C$), salt (PSU), OXY_oxy (mg O_2/L), NIT_amm (mg N/L), NIT_nit (mg N/L), PHS_frp (mg P/L), PHY_green (μg Chl-a/L)
- Outflows (`*_outflow.csv``): time (YYYY-MM-DD), flow (m^3/s)

3. Reproducibility post-processing

To reproduce results:

- Download GLM-AED from the [official website](#).
- Place all files for a reservoir in the same directory.
- Ensure file names match those referenced in the `*_glm2.nml`` configuration.
- Compile GLM with AED2 enabled.
- [Run the model](#).
- Outputs include `output.nc`` (full model results), `lake.csv`` (daily summary), `WQ_*.csv`` (time series at specific depths), `outlet_*.csv`` (outflow conditions), and `overflow.csv``.

Post-processing and [visualization](#) can be performed with `glm-py`` (Python) or `glmtools`` ([Rstudio](#)). More information about the model source code and new releases are available at [GitHub](#).

4. Citation

If using these datasets, please cite as DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.16888636]

5. License

This dataset is licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International (CC BY 4.0). You are free to share and adapt the material, provided appropriate credit is given.